

Institutional Assessment of the Impact of Microsoft Excel on Data Base Management in Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The study is an effort to assess the impact of Microsoft Excel on data based management in Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga – Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. Data for the study were obtained through face-to-face interview and the used of check list from 1st to 31st March, 2021. Both qualitative and descriptive techniques were employed in the analysis of the data. The result shows that Microsoft Excel was used to calculate, analyze, visualize, processes data and information by the use of columns and rows with formulas. Enables statistical thinking and enhances understanding of important ideas in statistics. It is recommended that holistic approach should be made in the development of information communication technology (ICT) in all spheres of governance in the study area and environs and also at the apex level; Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria (ARCN).

KEYWORDS: Institutional Impact, Microsoft Excel, Data Base Management, Student Enrolment, Staff Strength, Funding.

INTRODUCTION

Makrakis (2011) uses of Microsoft Excel in daily life is to perform the calculation, analysis, and visualization of data and information. Microsoft Excel is one of the most important workplace applications that help to organize the business system and processes of data and information by the use of columns and rows with formulas. Microsoft Excel Application is developed and marketed by Microsoft Inc. for Windows, Mac OS, Cloud computing, and Android users. In the excel spreadsheet users can do all kinds of mathematical, financial, logical calculation, data manipulation, data analysis, and visualization of information in quick ways. Excel is used by students, teachers, job seekers, managers, entrepreneurs, companies, retailers, distributors, freelancers, bloggers, and housewives in their daily life.

Microsoft Excel's first version was released 31 years ago on September 30, 1985. Today, the latest version you can download is version 16.0 or Excel 2016. Commonly people download & buy complete MS-Office. Because Microsoft Office Suite includes all official applications such as Microsoft Word, PowerPoint, Excel, Publisher, Outlook in one complete package. Excel spreadsheet is a group of 10, 48,576 rows and 16384 columns. Excel is in a table format in which one index is called a CELL. In Excel, there are three worksheets by default. A group of worksheets is called the workbook. Workbook and the electronic spreadsheet is now the synonym of Microsoft Excel. For a higher level of data calculation and manipulation, the use of the function library in Excel is important to utilize. Function library in Excel contains Financial, Logical, and text filtration formulas that are most important to practice for every excel learner. Excel also provides table styles and conditional formatting options for users. That is very beneficial to the visualization of data in colors, based on a condition in the cells (Schau, 2003).

Previous studies have found several skills such as communication and relationship building skills to be necessary in the workplace, while 80% of middle-skilled jobs have been found by online recruiters to require at least a basic understanding of Excel skills. Several reports have also found that advanced analytical skills, Excel in particular, results in increased marketability and increased compensation for graduates (Power, 2003).

For business students, spreadsheet knowledge is imperative in order for the likelihood of success in the job market. Therefore, a business school should pose the question "What Microsoft Excel skills are necessary to be taught to students for them to be successful in acquiring a job?" A second question can direct a business program by questioning, "What is the purpose of a college

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education?" Gerstein and Friedman (2016) point out that the answer to this question has varied over the years and still varies greatly today in different institutions. Should the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) curriculum focus predominantly on theory, concepts, critical thinking and knowledge? How much effort should be spent on skills development? With greater intensity employers are demanding skills and competencies that ensure students are productive and resilient in life in spite of the high degree of change being experienced in many professional fields.

Formby, Dawn, and Ellington, (2017) quotes Ronald Reagan in 1967 who said "we can no longer afford intellectual luxuries in universities." His point was that that education should create productive and economically sustainable members of society, implying that knowledge alone without skills is incomplete education. Over 80% of freshmen entering college say that the purpose of education is to get a good paying job and businesses are demanding basic skills beyond traditional topical knowledge in the employment process (Formby, Dawn, and Ellington, 2017). Freidman and Friedman (2015) make a compelling case that institutions must stress and teach skills that help students be successful and survive and thrive in the new knowledge economy. The need for graduates to start jobs with sound functional analytical skills, e.g. proficiency with Microsoft Excel, is therefore becoming more of a prerequisite for employment.

According to Formby, Dawn, and Ellington, (2017), found that students must have not only a proficiency in Excel, but have advanced skills. "A white paper study commissioned by Microsoft and released by IDC, October 2013, reported that the top two skills cited in over 14 million job postings for the top 60 job growth occupations of the economy were oral and written communications and Microsoft Office skills. Microsoft Excel was cited as the most ubiquitous analytics tool in business.

Geiger (2015) reported on a study finding that 78% of middle-skilled jobs require digital skills like Excel. Middle-skilled jobs are fast growing job categories that place more emphasis on skills than on the having a bachelor degree, and in many cases pay more than traditional jobs requiring the bachelor degree alone. These jobs require significant business understanding, but with the added emphasis on skills to apply quantitative business intelligence to decision making. Some could argue that business graduates should aspire to more senior management positions, but it is more appropriate to consider these middle-skilled positions as part of an accelerated path for business graduates into management.

The business education, coupled with the analytical skills with tools like Microsoft Excel place the business graduates in a highly favored position for future leadership. Business school graduates are therefore often in competition for these higher paying jobs and the skills proficiency makes the difference in the hiring selection (Geiger, 2015).

Soergel (2015) reports additional details on the middle-skill job study which concluded that salaries are 13-38% higher based on the analytical tools skills a candidate has when interviewed. Soergel concludes with the following quote from the study, "Jobs requiring advanced analytical tools skills offer the strongest opportunity for middle skill job seekers in terms of salary and growth as well as career advancement. Effectively, entire segments of the U.S. economy are off-limits to people who don't have basic analytical skills." Thus new BSBA graduates need to have these analytical skills to compete for these higher paying middle-skilled jobs.

There also appears to be a shift in hiring criteria such that skills are gaining in importance, and degree, school name, and GPA are dropping in importance, (Motunrayo, Mathew, Oladele, Hadiza, Abbajime and Sani, 2018). This message was also reinforced at the Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) workshop "Co-Lab Connecting Business Schools with Practice" in June 2016. In the session "Recruitment, Retention, and Engagement" panel speakers commented that talent acquisition was the #1 issue with many companies today and candidates with cyber and analytics skills and competencies were drawing significantly higher salary offers. Many companies are also establishing baseline quantitative assessment tests at part of the screening and interview process to ensure essential skills and competencies are present before hiring.

Vijay (2017) data analysis is very important aspect of work today for an online business or website owner and or a researcher (e-commerce, blog, forums, etc.). Such as tracking website visitors, products sell, customer reviews, marketing campaigns, user behavior, and events. Such work is very time and brain consuming especially when things are not going accordingly as planned. Microsoft Excel application provides great benefits for online business owners and customers. Such as filtering users' data by country, filter users by age, adding conditional formulas in big data, etc. are common daily tasks that can be handled smartly in excel.

Many online and offline organizations, companies and clients making it mandatory for virtually all staff to maintain their daily progress reports. It is not only beneficial for the employees but also for the companies to track daily progress reports. A table with Date, Time, Client, Task, Duration, and status will be created, accordingly as required in line with the organizational goal and objectives. The daily progress report is also very beneficial for students and teachers in an educational set up (Vijay, 2017).

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Despite the disruption caused by the Boko Haram insurgency on the educational sector of Borno state, as a result of computer application there are still several data sources available for the Borno State Education sector. The Borno State Universal Basic Education Commission (SUBEC) Education Management Information System (EMIS) teams have conducted their school based data collection exercise from One thousand three hundred and forty-six 1,346 schools. They have also gathered school level data about pupils, teachers, and buildings. The Census has collected data based on name, sex, rank, in (schools or Local Government Education Authority hierarchy) dates of birth, first appointment and last promotion, highest qualification, area of specialization and mobile telephone number for all pre-primary, or junior secondary school (JSS) teachers and for the Local Government Education Authority administrators. The Millennium Development Goals (MDG) Data Base Information System in the office of the presidency produced data for one thousand and seventy-eight (1,078) schools containing sixteen thousands five hundreds and ten (16,510) teachers and three hundred and thirty-seven thousand nine hundred and twenty-three (337,923) pupils (UBEC,2020).

PROBLEM SETTING AND RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Using Excel in Educational Institution for relevant activities that requires its application is possible solution for some of the challenges of data base management in most of our educational institutions. Therefore, its application will have positive impact on the data based management for the development of the educational sector. In spite the essential contribution of Microsoft Excel in the aspect of student enrolment, staff strength and funding of the college, the application of the Microsoft Excel is limited in the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno state, Nigeria. Considering the crucial role of Microsoft Excel in data base management in the sustainable development of education, there is the need for the institutional assessment of the impact of Microsoft Excel on this aspect of education in the study area.

In view of the above, this research work was undertaken to assess the impact of Microsoft Excel on data based management with particular reference to student enrolment, staff strength and funding in such a way to find some avenues of remedying its limitation to maximized it application to attain a higher degree of efficiency and effectiveness in data base management in the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria and for the overall development of the educational sector.

The main objective of the study is to assess the institutional impact of Microsoft Excel on Data Base Management in Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. evaluate the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the number of student enrolment in the study area;
- ii. examine the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the classification of staff strength in the study area;
- iii. assess the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the determination of the level of funding in the study area.

The output of this research work may be useful in decision making processes that has to do with the development of the educational sector in the area of provision of infrastructural facilities and other teaching and learning materials to the study area. It may also enable the school authority and other organization at the apex level for the organization of a program to improve the working capacity of the workers either by the way of sponsorship for the furtherance of the staff educational level or through the organization of workshop, seminars, for capacity building to improve their skillfulness in the discharge of their duties consequently attained higher degree of efficiency in the discharge of duty. The outcome of the research work may enable planners at the educational sector to formulate policies with respect to teacher employment, student enrolment and school funding policies towards the development of the educational sectors. The outcome of this research work may also result in comparative study analysis that may initiate educational system that will accelerate the much needed development; for example, the growth in technology is impacting on homes, streets, schools and other social, economic and political institutions thus introduction of educational system in line with required changes.

Data collection for the research work was carried out within the period of one (1) month, from 1st to 31st March, 2021, Considering the fact that within that period the students were in full session carrying out academic activities and the period coincided with the period of annual school record update submersible to the National Board for Technical Education, Kaduna, Nigeria (NBTE), an organization responsible for regulating the academic activities of the College.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

The study area was Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Kukawa Local Government Area of Borno State, located on the shores of the Nigerian portion of the Lake Chad Basin (FCFFT, 2009), re-located to National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, New Bussa, Niger state (NIFFRI) Zonal Office in Maiduguri in the year 2014 as a result of rumors of Boko Haram security threats. (See Appendix Ia & b, Pp. 14 & 15). The College was established by the proxy of the Federal Research Institutes

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Decree of 1975 (supplement to official gazette No. 61 volume 63 of 1975) which established Lake Chad Research Institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. As a result of the nationwide reorganization of Federal Research Institutes between 1988 to 1989, the supervision of the College was transferred to National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, New Bussa, Niger State of Nigeria, which is under the supervision of the Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria (ARC/N) Abuja, the apex body of all the agricultural research institutes in the country, Nigeria. The study area has a population of about three hundred and forty-eight (348) inhabitants, which comprises students, teaching and non-teaching staff and other auxiliary staff. The college concentrates on the training of fisheries personnel leading to the award of; Pre-National Diploma in Science and Technology, Vocational Certificate in Fisheries Technology, National Diploma in Fisheries Technology and Higher National Diploma in Fisheries Technology (FCFFT, 2009).

The targeted population for this study consist of two hundred and twenty (220) teaching staff, non-teaching staff and student from the study area, out of which thirty-five (35) respondents were used for the study.

Data for the study was obtained from primary and secondary source. Both the primary and secondary data were obtained through a face-to-face interview and the check list was used to elicit information from the respondents.

Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted for this study. In the first stage Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, - Maiduguri was purposively selected out of the Educational institutions in the state for this study. The second stage involved the selection of teaching, non-teaching staff and student in all the department of the institution and finally five (5) teaching staff, five (5) student in each of the three (3) departments were selected and five (5) non-teaching staff across all the three departments were also selected making a total of thirty-five (35) respondents for the study.

Both qualitative and descriptive technique were employed in the analysis of data to evaluate the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the number of student enrolment in the study area (objective i), examine the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the classification of staff strength in the study area (objective ii), assess the contribution of Microsoft Excel in the determination of the level of funding in the study area (objective iii).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contribution of Microsoft Excel in Student Enrolment in the Study Area

Based on the information obtained from the enrolment data of the institution for the 2017/2018 academic year shows that Pre-National Diploma (Pre-ND) full-time program enrolment was zero (0) for both male and female, part-time program enrolment was zero for both male and female (0). Last academic year turn out 2016/2017 session; Pre-National Diploma (Pre-ND) full-time program enrolment was zero (0) for both male and female, part-time program enrolment was zero (0) for both male and female. National Diploma (ND) full-time program enrolment for male twenty (20), female three (03) and part-time enrolment for male zero (0), female zero (0) for the year 2017/2018 academic session. Last academic year turn out 2016/2017 session; National Diploma (ND) full-time program enrolment for male five (05), female one (01) and part-time enrolment for male zero (0) female zero (0). Higher National Diploma (HND) full-time program enrolment for the year 2017/2018 academic session; male twenty (20), female three (03), part-time; male (0), female (0) and for the last academic session Higher National Diploma (HND) Program 2016/2017; full-time enrolment, male six (06) female one (01), part-time enrolment male (0) female (0). The total summary of enrolment and out-turn for the whole program by gender for the academic year 2017/2018; full-time program: male twenty (40), female six (06), part-time program; male zero (0), female zero (0). Last academic year out-turn 2016/2017 session full-time; male eleven (11), female two (02), part-time; male zero (0), female (0) (See Appendix II, Pp.16).

This result confirmed that of Gomes, Passeri and de Albergaria Barbosa (2006) Microsoft Excel is a versatile software offers a wide range of application ranging from data management to statistical analysis. The result shows consistency with the findings of Horgan (1999) Microsoft Excel can be used to demonstrate the statistical power of an experiment and to explore experimental variability.

Full-time enrolment at each level per program for the year 2017/2018 academic session; Pre-National Diploma (Pre-ND) Program male zero (0), female zero (0), National Diploma (ND) Program; Year One (1) male nine (09), female three (03), Year Two (2) male eleven (11), female zero (0), Total; male twenty (20), female three (03), Higher National Diploma (HND) Program; Year One (1) male sixteen (16), female one (01), Year Two (2) male four (04), female two (02), Total; male twenty (20), female three (03) and last out-turn for each program for the year 2016/2017 academic session; Pre-National Diploma (Pre-ND) Program male zero (0), female zero (0), National Diploma (ND) Program male five (05), female one (01) and Higher National Diploma (HND) Program male five (05), female one (01) respectively (See Appendix III, Pp.17).

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This result confirmed that of Makrakis (2011) uses of Microsoft Excel in daily life is to perform the calculation, analysis, visualization of data and information. Microsoft Excel is one of the most important workplace applications that help to organize the business system and processes of data and information by the use of columns and rows with formulas. The result shows consistency with the finding of Vijay (2017) Microsoft Excel software provides very wide features and functionalities for everyday official works. The various uses of Microsoft Excel features in daily, based on different types of users in the educational sector. Interesting cells can be highlighted in colors, emphasize important values and visualize data using bars and charts.

CONTRIBUTION OF MICROSOFT EXCEL IN STAFF STRENGTH CLASSIFICATION IN THE STUDY AREA

The contribution of Microsoft Excel in the study area shows teaching staff and non-teaching staff distribution by academic qualification, membership of a professional body as per their designation departmentally and non-teaching staff distribution by Hatis/Contiss level for the year 2017/2018 academic session.

The summary of the findings in the department of fisheries technology revealed that members of staff registered with professional body appeared highest with total number of ten (10) members of teaching staff with membership of professional body, followed by five (05) members of teaching staff with Higher National Diploma (HND) and four (04) with Master Degree (MSc) all were in the male category. The least observation was discovered under the Doctorate (PhD) classification with one (01) also appeared under the male category (See Appendix IV, Pp.18).

In the department of basic science, the highest observation recorded was in the membership of a professional body with eight (08) followed by first (1st) Degree with six (06) and five (05) with Master Degree (MSc). The least of the findings revealed one (01) under Doctorate (PhD) classification. All the findings recorded appeared to be under male category (See Appendix V, Pp.19).

This result confirmed that of Nash and Quon (1996) implemented Microsoft Excel to develop statistical thinking.

Under the department of general study's findings revealed that teaching staff with Master Degree (MSc) and also teaching staff with membership of a professional body were four (04) in each of the observation and both appeared under the male category. The least was under the Doctorate (PhD) with zero (0) observation (See Appendix VI, Pp.20).

Findings under the non-teaching staff distribution by HATISS/CONTISS levels indicates that the highest number of staff recorded were under HATISS/CONTISS six (06) and seven (07) comprising sixteen (16) total number of non-teaching staff in each HATISS/CONTISS level. Followed by nine (09) total number non-teaching staff under the classification of HATISS/CONTISS eight (08) and zero (0) number of non-teaching staff were recorded under HATISS/CONTISS two (02), ten (10) and fourteen (14) (See Appendix VII, Pp.21).

This result shows consistency with the findings of Khleitner, (2007), Borovenik, (2007) in some studies Microsoft Excel was used to illustrate combinatorial ideas. The result confirmed that of Price and Zhang (2007) used of excel to enhance understanding important ideas in statistics.

Contribution of Microsoft Excel in the Determination of the Level of Funding in the Study Area

Finding revealed Microsoft Excel enables the determination of the level of funding in the study area in the aspects of total amount sought, total amount approved and total amount released under the categories of capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure and other special grant such as research grant, teaching grant and rehabilitation special fund for a given period of time usually a year (See Appendix VIII, Pp.22).

This result confirmed that of Makrakis (2011) in the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet users can do all kinds of mathematical, financial, logical calculation, data manipulation, data analysis and visualization of information in quick ways. This result shows consistency with the finding of Schau (2003) function library in Microsoft Excel contains financial, logical and text filtration formulas that are most important to practice for every excel learner. Microsoft Excel also provides table styles and conditional formatting options for users. That is very beneficial to the visualization of data in colors, based on a condition in the cells.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The impact of Microsoft Excel on data base management in education cannot be overemphasized owing to the fact that Microsoft Excel as versatile software have offered a wide range of data base management which have demonstrated experimentally and explored experimental variability and illustrated combinatorial ideas and enhanced understanding of important ideas in statistics relating to student enrolment, staff strength and the level of funding in the study area. Microsoft Excel enhances student, teacher and non-teaching staff to use their intellectual capability in the conversion of raw data in to meaningful, tracked research goals, performed calculations faster and accurately and has enabled quick visualization of the level of funding although Microsoft excel

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is not adequately institutionally used in the study area. Therefore, it worth mentioning that Microsoft Excel application in the study area should be compel to both student, teacher and non-academic staff as opined by friedman and friedman (2015) that institutions must stress and teach skills that help students be successful and survive and thrive in the new knowledge economy. The outcome of the study shows that Microsoft Excel have impacted positively on data base management in the study area in the aspects of student enrolment, classification of staff strength and the determination of the level of funding but there is the need for improvement. The following recommendations were made: -

- 1) Capacity building training program should be organized for both the teachers and students of the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria to acquire proficiency in Microsoft Excel application with emphasis to data base management.
- 2) Microsoft Excel course should be introduced and incorporated in to the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria academic curriculum as compulsory course.
- 3) Proficiency in Microsoft Excel application either by working experience or academic qualification back up with authentic document as evidence should be made pre-requisite requirement for employment in to the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria.
- 4) Proficiency in Microsoft Excel application either by working experience or academic qualification back up with authentic document as evidence should be made pre-requisite requirement for admission in to the Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga, Borno State of Nigeria academic programs.
- 5) Appropriate authorities at the apex level e.g. Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria, (ARCN) Abuja should be made, duly and accordingly informed for the implementation of the above as appropriate.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abubakar J. I. (2007) Ground Water Management of the Nigerian Sector of the Lake Chad Basin. A Paper Delivered at the Regional Round Table, Organized by the Directorate of Technical Co-operation in Africa (DTCA) in Conjunction with University of Maiduguri, Borno State on 22nd February, 2007
- 2) AFP (2015) Agence France Press (AFP) Map of Borno State of Nigeria; Showing the Capital City, Maiduguri
- 3) Borovcnik, M. (2007). Das Sammelbildproblem Ñ Rosinen Und Semmeln Und Verwandtes:
- 4) FCFFT (2009) College Prospectus; Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga – Borno State, Nigeria 2009. Email: Bagafishcol@Yahoo.Com
- 5) FCFFT: ICT (2021) Information Communication Technology, Centre; Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Baga – Borno State, Nigeria. Email: Bagafishcol@Yahoo.Com
- 6) Formby, S. K., Dawn, M.B., and Ellington, V., (2017) Microsoft Excel: Is It an Important Job Skill for College Graduates? Information System Education Journal (ISEDJ) ISSN: 1545-679X: 2017 ISCAP (Information Systems and Computing Academic Professionals) <http://www.isedj.org>; <http://iscap.info>
- 7) Friedman, H. H. and Friedman, L W. (2015) Six Steps to transform an Ordinary College in to an Exceptional Institution. Available at SSRN.
- 8) Geiger, B. (2015) Your Excel Skills could land you your next job. <http://fortune.com/2015/03/06/microsoft-excel-jobs/>
- 9) Gerstein, M. and Friedman, H. H. (2016) Rethinking Higher Education: Focusing on Skills and Competencies, Psych sociological Issues in Human Resource Management, 4(2), 104- 121.
- 10) Gomes, P. P. Passeri, L. A., & De Albergaria Barbosa, J. R. (2006). A 5-Year Retrospective Study of Zygomatico-Orbital Complex and Zygomatic Arch Fractures in Sao Paulo State, Brazil. *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 64(1), 63ñ67.
- 11) Horgan, G. W. (1999). Use of Spreadsheets for Demonstrating Experimental Power and Variability. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 7(1). [http://Www.Deakin.Edu.Au/%7Elim/Kflim/Papers/2003_Spreadshe_et CCEN/S_preadshEetbs](http://Www.Deakin.Edu.Au/%7Elim/Kflim/Papers/2003_Spreadshe_et_CCEN/S_preadshEetbs)
- 12) K,Hleitner, M. (2007). Sammelbildproblem: Eine Simulation Mit Excel. *Stochastik in Der Schule*, 27(1), 24ñ26.
- 13) Makrakis, V. (2011). ICT-Enabled Education for Sustainable Development: Merging Theory with Praxis. In M. Youssef & S. Aziz Anwar (Eds.), Proceedings of The 4th Annual Conference On E-Learning Excellence in The Middle East 2011 Ñ in Search of New Paradigms for Reengineering Education (Pp. 410ñ419). Dubai, UAE: Hamdan Bin Mohammed E University.

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- 14) Motunrayo F. A., Mathew P., Oladele, A., Hadiza M., Abbajime M. And Sani J. (2018) Teaching Distress: An Assessment of the Impact of Protracted Violence Due to Insurgence On the Primary School Teaching Work Force in Borno State, Nigeria.
- 15) Nash, J., & Quon, T. (1996). Issues in Teaching Statistical Thinking with Spreadsheets. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 4(1).
- 16) Power, D. J. (2003) A Brief History of Spreadsheets.
- 17) Price, B., & Zhang, X. (2007). The Power of Doing: A Learning Exercise That Brings the Central Limit Theorem to Life. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 5(2), 405ñ411.
- 18) Schau, C. (2003). Studentsí Attitudes: The ðotherí Important Outcome in Statistics Education. Paper Presented at The Joint Statistical Meeting, Section On Statistics Education, San Francisco, CA.
- 19) UBEC (2020) Universal Basic Education Commission, 2010 Basic Education Profile National and Regional Statistics Facts and Figures: Northeast Region. Universal Basic Education Commission, Abuja – Nigeria. Pp. 17-23.
- 20) Vijay S. (2017) Top Eight (8) Most Productive Uses of Microsoft Excel in Daily Life. SOLUTECH-Power by Creative Themes.

APPENDIX 1A: STUDY AREA MAP

Map showing Maiduguri, the Borno State Capital

Source: Agence France Press (2015)

APPENDIX 1b: STUDY AREA MAP

Map showing the Lake Chad Area (Baga)

Source: Abubakar (2007)

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APPENDIX II: SUMMARY OF ENROLMENT AND OUT-TURN, 2017/2018 ACADEMIC SESSION

SUMMARY OF ENROLMENT & OUT-TURN								
PROGRAMME TITLE	ENROLMENT				LAST ACADEMIC YEAR OUT-TURN:			
	FULL TIME		PART TIME		FULL TIME		PART TIME	
	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE
PRE-NATIONAL DIPLOMA (PRE-ND)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NATIONAL DIPLOMA (ND)	20	3	0	0	5	1	0	0
HIGHER NATIONAL DIPLOMA (HND)	20	3	0	0	6	1	0	0
POST HND (PHND)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
OTHERS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	40	6	0	0	11	2	0	0

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Source: ICT Centre, FCFFT, Baga, 2021

APPENDIX III: FULL-TIME ENROLMENT AND OUT-TURN FOR THE YEAR 2017/2018 ACADEMIC SESSION

FULL-TIME ENROLMENT & OUT-TURN																			
PROGRAMME	PRELIM		NATIONAL DIPLOMA						HIGHER NATIONAL DIPLOMA						2016/2017				
			YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL 1 & 2		LAST ND OUT-TURN		YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL 1 & 2		LAST HND OUT-TURN		
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	
PRE-ND (SCIENCE & TECH.)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
ND FISHERIES TECHNOLOGY			9	3	11	0	20	3	5	1									
HND FISHERIES TECHNOLOGY												16	1	4	2	20	3	5	1
TOTAL	0	0	9	3	11	0	20	3	5	1	16	1	4	2	20	3	5	1	

Source: ICT Centre, FCFFT Baga, 2021

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APPENDIX IV: TEACHING STAFF DISTRIBUTION BY QUALIFICATION, DEPARTMENT OF FISHERIES TECHNOLOGY

TEACHING STAFF DISTRIBUTION BY QUALIFICATIONS																						
STAFF DESIGNATION	TEACHING STAFF																					
	FULL - TIME TEACHING STAFF										PART - TIME TEACHING STAFF										TOTAL (FULL-TIME & PART-TIME)	
	PHD		MASTERS		1ST DEG.		HND		NO. OF STAFF REGISTERED WITH PROFESSIONAL BODY		PHD		MASTERS		1ST DEG.		HND		NO. OF STAFF REGISTERED WITH PROFESSIONAL BODY			
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
CHIEF LECTURER	0	0								0	0											
PRINCIPAL LECTURER	0	0								0	0											
SENIOR LECTURER	0	0								0	0											
LECTURER I			3	0						3	0											
LECTURER II	1	0	1	0						2	0											
LECTURER III					1	0				1	0											
ASST. LECTURER					2	1				1	0											
CHIEF INSTRUCTOR								1	0	1	0											
ASST. CHIEF INSTRUCTOR								0	0	0	0											
PRINCIPAL INSTRUCTOR								2	1	2	1											
SENIOR INSTRUCTOR								0	0	0	0											
INSTRUCTOR I								2	0	0	0											
INSTRUCTOR II																						
CHIEF TECHNOLOGIST																						
ASST. CHIEF TECHNOLOGIST																						
PRINCIPAL TECHNOLOGIST																						
SENIOR TECHNOLOGIST																						
TECHNOLOGIST I																						
TECHNOLOGIST II																						
TOTAL	1	0	4	1	3	1	0	5	1	10	1	0	0	0	0							

Source: ICT Centre, FCFFT, Baga, 2021

APPENDIX V: TEACHING STAFF DISTRIBUTION BY QUALIFICATION, DEPARTMENT OF BASIC SCIENCES

TEACHING STAFF DISTRIBUTION BY QUALIFICATIONS																						
STAFF DESIGNATION	TEACHING STAFF																					
	FULL - TIME TEACHING STAFF										PART - TIME TEACHING STAFF										TOTAL (FULL-TIME & PART-TIME)	
	PHD		MASTERS		1ST DEG.		HND		NO. OF STAFF REGISTERED WITH PROFESSIONAL BODY		PHD		MASTERS		1ST DEG.		HND		NO. OF STAFF REGISTERED WITH PROFESSIONAL BODY			
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
CHIEF LECTURER	0	0								0	0											
PRINCIPAL LECTURER	0	0								0	0											
SENIOR LECTURER	1	0								1	0											
LECTURER I			4	1						4	1											
LECTURER II			1	0	1	0				2	0											
LECTURER III			0	0	2	0																
ASST. LECTURER					3	0				0	0				1	0					0	0
CHIEF INSTRUCTOR																						
ASST. CHIEF INSTRUCTOR																						
PRINCIPAL INSTRUCTOR																						
SENIOR INSTRUCTOR																						
INSTRUCTOR I																						
INSTRUCTOR II																						
CHIEF TECHNOLOGIST																						
ASST. CHIEF TECHNOLOGIST																						
PRINCIPAL TECHNOLOGIST								1	0	1	0											
SENIOR TECHNOLOGIST								0	1	0	0											
TECHNOLOGIST I																						
TECHNOLOGIST II																						
TOTAL	1	0	5	1	6	0	1	1	8	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: ICT Centre,FCFFT, Baga, 2021

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APPENDIX VIII: FUNDING

FUNDING						
	CAPITAL EXPENDITURE	RECURRENT EXPENDITURE	RESEARCH GRANT	TEACHING GRANT	REHABILITATION SPECIAL FUND	TOTAL
AMOUNT SOUGHT						
AMOUNT APPROVED						
AMOUNT RELEASED						

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Source: ICT Centre, FCFFT, Baga, 2021

Note: Data Restricted for Confidential Purpose (Finance)